

Challenges Faced in the Sector of Tourism in Assam with Special Reference to Rural Tourism

Paper Id : 18580 Submission Date : 11/02/2024 Acceptance Date : 19/02/2024 Publication Date : 25/02/2024

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11126602

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Rumi Barlow

Assistant Professor
Department Of History
Samaguri College
Nagaon, Assam, India

Abstract

Tourism of Assam is based on wildlife, natural beauty, unique flora and fauna, holy shrines, lush green tea gardens, turbulent rivers, vibrant and colourful cultural festivals. Rural tourism is of remote place based on local community. In rural tourism people can enjoy the local tradition, culture, and even traditional food. hereby people get fresh air and natural environment free from the noise and air pollution of cities. Though Assam tourism has tremendous potentialities to be used as a source of economic development of the state's economy, it is still facing some challenges. So, in this paper the investigator intends to study the major challenges facing by Assam tourism specially in rural areas and also will try to find out the solutions of the problems faced by tourism of Assam. The present study uses both primary and secondary data. To collect primary data five tourists spots of the state namely Pabitora, Manas, Hajo, SuryaPahar and Chandubi are selected. The overview of the tourism in Assam in general and the same in Pabitora, Manas, Hajo, SuryaPahar and Chandubi in particular have been analysed on the basis of secondary data. The tourist places of Assam have some challenges like lack of awareness of local people about the potentialities of the places, lack of promotion in social media, underdeveloped transport system, inadequate capital investment in this sector both by govt and private parties, lack of proper planning and development, insecurity and insurgency, political apathy, absence of well trained tourist guide etc. and of course infrastructural issues too.

Keywords Tourism, Assam, Challenges, Type, Tourist Spot.

Introduction

At present tourism is considered as an important industry which has vast scope for the generation of income and employment. Tourism is one of world's fastest growing industries, a major source of foreign exchange earner of a nation. Tourism helps a lot in economic development of a nation. It boosts the revenue of the economy; It creates thousands of jobs, develop the infrastructure of a country and plants a sense of cultural activities. Tourism boosts the revenue of the economy; it creates thousands of jobs, develops the infrastructure of a country, and plants a sense of cultural activities.

Assam is best known for her unique natural beauty. Assam is also regarded as paradise of tourists. Tourism of Assam is based on wildlife, natural beauty, unique flora and fauna, pilgrims and historical monuments, lush green tea gardens, turbulent rivers, vibrant and colourful cultural festivals. All these make Assam one of the best destinations of the tourists. However, like any other tourists destination, Assam also faces its fair share of challenges that hinder the growth and development of its tourism sector. In this paper, the investigator intends to make a comprehensive study of the challenges faced by the tourists in Assam, aiming to shed light on the key areas that require attention and intervention. By understanding these challenges, we can pave the way towards sustainable tourism practices, ensuring the preservation of Assam's unique attractions while providing memorable experiences for visitors.

Rural tourism is a type of tourism placed on remote areas. In this tourism tourist can enjoy the local tradition, culture and traditional food items too. Here people get fresh air and natural environment free from the pollution of the cities. In rural tourism local people are getting involve directly. So they are benefited a lot from this type of tourism. Besides local

people get chance to earn their livelihood with the help of this tourism. In this study the investigator intends to study and find out the potentialities of rural tourism, its challenges and remedial measures.

Tourism of Assam faces a range of challenges that impact various aspects of the tourism experience. Infrastructure deficiencies pose significant hurdles, including inadequate transportation networks, lack of quality accommodation and insufficient public convenience. These limitations affect tourists' accessibility, comfort and convenience, hindering their overall experience. Safety and security concerns also emerge as critical challenges faced by tourists in Assam. Ensuring the safety of visitors, particularly in remote areas and wildlife sanctuaries, requires robust security measures, efficient emergency response system and awareness campaigns to build confidence among tourists.

Connectivity is another vital aspect that needs attention. Most of the remote areas of Assam yet not connected with railways. Besides the routes to those destinations are not so convenient for public or private vehicles too. So, tourists have to face a lot of problems due to lack of proper connectivity. So, it is very essential to take steps to improve connectivity of those remote areas to exercise full tourism potential. Besides these lack of proper promotion of cultural heritage within the country as well as of the world is another challenge of rural tourism. So, it is utmost important to take strong and attractive strategies to promote Assam's heritage, culture, tradition to attract tourists from different parts of the world.

Aim of study

1. To study the prospects and challenges of Rural Tourism in Assam
2. To suggest measures to meet the issues related to Rural Tourism in Assam.

Review of Literature

Lane (1994), in his study on Rural Tourism mentions that "The concept of Rural Tourism is tourism located in the rural areas i.e., the areas which are rural in scale, character and function reflecting the unique patterns of the rural environment, economy, history and location. In that sense, rural tourism is a tool which can increase the capacity of rural communities to control their rural milieu more gainfully."

Mishra and Soudal (2008), in their study stated that, "the rural tourism is actually an activity that takes place in the countryside. It includes farm/agricultural business enterprise, cultural, nature adventure and eco-tourism. As against typical tourism enterprise, a rural tourism enterprise has typical characteristics; it's experience-oriented; the location area is usually less inhibited, it's preponderantly in natural environments and it supports the preservation of culture, heritage, and traditions especially locally.

Sharpley and Vass (2006) in their study stated that, "Rural Tourism exists in some form or the other. In various tourist destinations, the main centres of attraction are located in rural areas; some of them are mountains, lakes, national parks, cultural sites and others. Apart from these tourist spots, this sort of tourism can also be extended to experiencing actual rural lifestyles and locals of the area may readily welcome tourists into their life. Rural tourism has emerged as an important means of addressing the complex socio-economic challenges of the rural communities following the decline of the traditional agricultural economy."

Ramakumar & Shinde (2008) in their study on Tourism stated that "Rural Tourism is developing as one of the best options available with its proven results in the west, to promote incredible India both for local and foreign tourists. The current estimated market for rural tourism in India is around Rs. 4, 300 cores per annum. It has the potential of appealing to both foreign and local tourists."

Bezbaruah, C.J. (2022) in his study on Rural Tourism stated that the rural tourism potentially in the state is high as 98.4 % of all the geographical areas of the state are rural. Rural tourism can turn out to be a boon for society as it will certainly help to develop the financial status of the host community.

Saikia, M. (2020) in his study on Problems and prospects of Tourism in Assam Stated that Assam has developed a considerable image as a tourism spot. It offers all the potentialities to become Assam as tourist destinations. The study concludes that the prospects of Assam tourism exist through heavily dependent on economic and infrastructure development. To ensure all round development there should be collaboration from tourism authority and academicians, from the public sector and private sector and also from civil society and local community.

Tripathy, Abhishek in his study on challenges faced by the tourist in Assam stated that the tourism sector in Assam faces a lot of challenges that needs to address to attract more tourists. These challenges include inadequate infrastructure, safety and security concerns, connectivity issue, untrained guides etc.

Mishra and Saudal (2008) in their study on rural tourism stated that rural tourism is actually an activity that takes place in the countryside. It is multifarious and should entail agricultural, cultural, nature adventure and eco-tourism.

Methodology

Method : In this paper descriptive method is used. The data for the study is secondary as the study is related to the potentiality and the challenges of rural tourism in the state.

Sample size: A sample of 200 tourists has been randomly selected from 5 spots of Assam

The present study covers the following five spots:

1. Chandubi : Chandubi Lake is a natural lake located in Rabha Hasong Council, Kamrup District of Assam. The lake is located at the foot of Garo Hills surrounded by Assam and Meghalaya. The lake attracts migratory birds during winter.

2. Hajo : Hajo is an ancient pilgrimage centre for three religions of Hinduism, Islam and Buddhism. Hajo is home to a number of temples and sacred places including Hayagriva Madhava Mandir, Powa-mecca, Kameswar temple, Joy Durga Temple, Dhopaguri Satra etc.

3. Manas: Manas National Park is situated in the Himalayan foothills. The park is known for its rare and endangered endemic wildlife such as Assam rooted turtle, hidden hare, golden langur and pygmy hog. Manas is also known for its population of the wild water buffalo.

4. Pobitora: Pobitora Wildlife sanctuary is situated on the bank of the Brahmaputra River in Morigaon district of Assam. It was declared in 1987 and covers 38.85 sq.km, providing grassland and wetland habitat for the Indian rhinoceros. It has a dense population of the Great Indian one-horned rhinoceros.

5. Surya Pahar : Surya Pahar is located about 12 km southeast of Goalpara and about 132 km northwest from Guwahati. Surya Pahar is an archaeological site in Assam. The site is a hilly terrain where several rocks –cut Shivalingas, votive stupas and the deities of Hindu, Buddhist and Jain are scattered in an area of about one km.

Analysis

Rural Tourism in Assam

Assam's tourism has always been nature centric. Though the state had its struggles to emerge as a tourism destination after the independence, the tourism board of the state initially and mostly focused on the natural segment of tourism to draw tourists attention towards Assam. The natural elements of tourism in the state are undoubtedly one of the best spots in the country and also have been able to successfully draw a significant number of tourists every year. However, as the tourism market has changed over the years, depending on only one segment of the tourism would not be beneficial for state tourism. It is not that the state tourism has not given a chance to the other tourism segments at all. However, the prime focus has always been on the natural flora and fauna of the state. Assam is economically backward yet naturally and culturally rich state of India.

Tourism, in general is one of the largest industries in the world generating billions of dollars every year. In India there are states which solely depend on tourism industry. The potentiality of becoming a state like this is high when we talk about Assam as a state, which is culturally and naturally very rich. Though there are various segments and aspects of tourism that are available to explore in the market, Rural Tourism is one of the segments which has the highest potential to grow and develop the state as well as its people. Hence, it becomes important to understand the nature of Rural Tourism and how it works. Rural Tourism, in simple language, is a type of community-based tourism, where the tourist gets involved with the host community and experiences the culture and tradition directly by participating in the process. As community-based tourism, rural tourism may both, directly and indirectly, affect the economical, socio-cultural, and environmental factors in a particular geographical location.

Rural Tourism, if planned and executed well, may create employment for the host community and eventually generate income for them. This type of tourism helps rural people to rise their standard of living and make them conscious about their living standard, education. Through rural tourism local people get a chance to earn their livelihood involving local and allied business and get a chance to meet people from other states even foreigners too.

With the continuous inflow of tourists, the rural area or the villages will see a rise in the income level of individual families, education and health infrastructure, etc. As the income of the local population grows, so will the prices of land, housing, and demand for other goods and services. These economic growths will ultimately help the government to see an upward growth in revenue generation for the state. Apart from the economic

changes to the host community and the place, the environmental and other socio-cultural factors are to get affected as well.

Challenges of Rural Tourism in Assam:

Rural Tourism in Assam is still in starting level and a lot of planning and execution is required both at grassroots and in management levels. Rural tourism of Assam confronts with some problems. Here some of the challenges of Rural Tourism---

a. Lack of Communication and Road Infrastructure: Lack of transportation and other communication services like mobile network and internet are serious issue in the state. Due to inconvenient connectivity most of the rural areas of Assam are cut off urban areas. This creates a gap between the tourism spot and the tourists.

b. Lack of Decent Accommodation Facilities: In rural areas there are no hotels or lodge like towns or cities, but still there must be provision for comfortable lodging and hygienic food that required for the tourists to stay. It is seen that in rural areas the number of hotels or lodges are very less and the existing hotels are not convenient to stay.

c. Lack of awareness among the host communities: In rural tourism, the big challenge is that the lack of awareness of the village community about rural tourism and its benefit. Most of the members of the host communities are not aware of the potential that it holds. They are quite ignorant of this concept except a few.

d. Lack of sufficient tour guides: The insufficient amount of tour guides from both the government as well as the private sector is another big challenge to rural tourism. Tourists are often found in a state of confusion without the proper guidance from tourism stakeholders.

e. Lack of promotion of cultural integrity: Assam is full of diverse and vibrant cultural heritage. However, the lack of effective promotion and preservation of its cultural integrity can be a challenge. Insufficient emphasis on showcasing traditional arts, crafts, music, dance forms and festivals can limit the cultural experiences offered to tourists. Proper promotion and preservation of the state's cultural heritage can enhance its appeal as tourist destination.

Medical facility: The health care facility is the prime need of the rural tourism. While some areas in Assam have well –equipped medical facilities, others may lack proper healthcare infrastructure, including hospitals and emergency services. This can pose a challenge in ensuring the safety and well being of tourists, especially in case of emergencies or health issues.

f. Lack of ATM facility: Unavailability of ATM facility can create problem for tourists who rely on cash transactions in remote areas or less developed regions, tourists may struggle to find ATM's to withdraw money or make necessary payments. This can cause inconvenience and limit tourists' spending options.

Conclusion

Assam is a land of opportunities, especially when it comes to tourism. The rural tourism potentiality in the state is high as 98.4% of all the geographical areas of the state are rural. With this huge amount of rural areas, the potentiality of developing rural tourism in the state grows much higher than anything else. However, this needs a continuous approach and well-designed planning. Participation of both the public and private sector are required. The host community has to be well aware of the opportunities that they will get from rural tourism. Rural tourism can turn out to be a boon for society as it will certainly help to develop the financial status of the host community. Rural tourism also gives a window to the host community to showcase their cultural values to the outer world. The development of socio-cultural values, the economy of the society and the government are all interlinked with rural tourism. The only criterion which is required at the moment is to identify the true potentiality of rural tourism and act accordingly by both public and private sector tourism stakeholders.

Suggestions for the future Study

As a contemporary tourism sector, rural tourism in Assam has too many loopholes and has a tremendous possibility to improve. With proper planning and execution, the concept of rural tourism in Assam shall not take too much time to levitate. Based on the above discussion on rural tourism products and challenges, here are a few of the recommendations that can help the state to develop itself as a rural tourism destination in the near future –

i) The first thing that Assam lacks in rural tourism development is a structured state

tourism policy to develop Rural Tourism in the state. Though the government of Assam recently launched a scheme named 'Amar Alohi', meaning 'our guest' which focuses on tourist home stays by the local people. This scheme encourages the host community to convert their homes into home stays by letting one or two rooms of their house to the tourists. Though this scheme sounds good on paper, no further action has been taken to promote or regulate the scheme to the general population. Hence, a structured tourism policy focusing on rural tourism is the need of the hour.

ii) Along with a dedicated tourism policy, the government should allocate its attention to connectivity development. Identification of prospective rural areas and proper road connectivity to those places are very much required at the moment.

iii) Developing tourist lodges and hotels in rural areas for the tourist to stay in is another factor of recommendation. With the help of schemes like 'Amar Alohi', the host community will get benefitted; however, the same has to be streamlined to be more effective. Private sector participation is also required for the state to emerge as a potential rural tourism destination.

iv) Awareness programs on rural tourism for both the host community as well as the various travel and tour agency are required. The more they will know about the financial benefits, the more they will be encouraged to get involved with the process. Road shows, conferences, and public meetings can be organised in the district and block-wise to draw attention at a grassroots level.

v) Encouraging tour operators, travel agencies and other related stakeholders to develop the idea of keeping and training tour guides is the need of the hour. Assam has a very low amount of qualified tour guides who can direct and advise the tourists whenever they require. Proper training and recruiting should be done from both the public and private sectors to encourage more on having quality tour guides.

References

1. Ahmed, Nawaz. Sustainable Tourism Development in Uttarakhand Region of India, International Journal of Management and Social Sciences Research (IJMSSR) ISSN: 2319 4421, 2013 April, 2(4).
2. Arunothaipipat, Rosamarin. Human Resource Management of Small Independent Hotels: A Case Study of Chaam Beach, Phetchaburi, Thailand, Small Business Management, Bangkok: Text and Journal Publication, 2011.
3. Bordoloi, Anjan K, Kalita, Archana. Rural tourism: an important sector underpinning growth and development of rural Assam, International Journal of Management Research and Review, 2012 Dec, 2(12). Article No-7, 2069-2076 ISSN: 2249-7196.
5. Das, Dr. Dilip Kumar, Ray, Nilanjan, Developing infrastructure for promotion of rural tourism in the state of West Bengal: A study on Kamarpukur, International journal of research in commerce & management, 2012 May, 3(5). ISSN 0976-2183.
6. Hall, Colin Michael & Boyd, Stephen W, Nature-based Tourism in Peripheral Areas: Development or Disaster? 21 of Aspects of tourism, Channel View Publications; 2005. ISBN: 1845410009, 9781845410001.
7. Karanwal, Abhinav, Dabral, Paritosh. The Scope of Rural Tourism in the Hills of Mussoorie, Digital Repository, Manipal University Libraries; c2014.
8. Karri, Gopal Naidu, Scope of Agritourism in India, PGDMA Dissertation, ICAR- National Academy of Agricultural Research Management, Hyderabad; c2016.
9. Khairil Wahidin Awang, Wan Melissa Wan Hassan, Mohd Salehuddin Mohd Zahari. Tourism Development: A Geographical Perspective, Asian Social Science, 2009, 5(5).
10. Maricia, Drutu, Dorobantu, Maria Roxana. The relationship between agro tourism and rural tourism among with the sustainable development concept, Development activities from rural environment, The Tribuna Economica Journal. 2013;33:82-83.
11. Meena, Shivraj. Rural tourism impact, challenges and opportunities in Rajasthan, The Journal of Bengal Geographer, 2015 Oct IV(IV). ISSN 2319-619X.
12. Mili, Nitashree, Rural Tourism Development: An Overview of Tourism in the Tipam Phakey Village of Naharkatia in Dibrugarh District, Assam (India), International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 2012 Dec, 2(12) ISSN 2250-3153.

13. Okech, Roselyne, Haghiri, Morteza, George, Babu P. Rural tourism as a sustainable development alternative: an analysis with special reference to Luanda, Kenya, Culture-Revista De Cultura E Turismo, ISSN: 1982.5838, 2012 Aug, 6(03).
14. Ramakumar A, Shinde Rajashree, Product Development and Management in Rural Tourism (With Reference to Maharashtra), Conference on Tourism in India – Challenges Ahead, IIM (K), 2008 May.
15. Sharpley R, Vass A. Tourism, farming and diversification: An attitudinal study. Tourism Management. 2006;27:1040-1052.